

PROBLEMATIC ASPECTS OF WORKING TIME IN FOREIGN COUNTRIES

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Annotation: The article deals with the issues of legal regulation of the employee's working time with the study of foreign experience, which analyzes various aspects of issues related to working time in foreign countries, flexible mode of regulation of working hours, working hours, working week.

Key words: labor legislation, labor relations, working hours, working week, working hours in foreign countries.

The international labour standards are a normative element of labour law, one of the achievements of modern development and the development of social policy instruments by the joint efforts of the international community, which are reflected in the results efforts by states to introduce social values into the market economy.

The content of these standards is a reflection of the experience of many countries, the formation of the most valuable and comprehensive principles and bases of the national labor law, the creation of practical rules with the participation of lawyers, the existing system of labor legal regulation, various views and approaches, various political forces and interests. The result of a collision of concepts involves finding a compromise legal formula that will be converted into international documents.

One of the crucial objectives of the research is to analyze and describe the terms of the working hours in legal studies.

To date, the Republic of Uzbekistan has acceded to 70 basic human rights documents by the UN became the participant of 10 main international treaties. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights, which includes the basic democratic principles and requirements of the international community in the field of human rights and freedoms, has become a political and legal basis for the formation of an international system of law in this field. the right to a reasonable day-to-day rest and the right to paid leave [1].

In addition, the International Labor Organization (ILO) is the main convention in the field of working hours of the International Labor Organization No. 47 "On reducing working hours for up to forty hours", which the Republic of Uzbekistan acceded to in 1995 and these international norms are also found in national legislation. In addition, the International Labor Organization and other

international humanitarian organizations set out measures to prevent employees from getting sick at work, to prevent them from working longer than prescribed [2].

According to recent OECD labor market research, the study has been conducted in 38 countries. These countries include Germany, Denmark, Switzerland, Austria and Luxembourg, but Mexico, Costa Rica and South Korea are the leading countries in terms of actual working hours.

The most industrious workers in Europe are the UK, Greece and Portugal. Despite working 43.7 hours a week, the British often stay at work. Portuguese people work 8 hours and 48 minutes a day, an average of 48 hours per week. However, according to experts, the employees are not fully engaged in their duties during this time.

In Asia, people work a little harder. In China, for example, the average daily working time is 10 hours, with 6 days a week. The result is 60 hours of work per week. During this time, the Chinese will be given 20 minutes for lunch and 10 days for a vacation.

Of the Labor Code of the Republic of June 5, 1994 Paragraph 39 provides that an employer may be entitled to another work schedule if it is not possible to use a normal work schedule schedule [3]. Also, one of the types of working hours is non-permanent work time for certain categories of workers. In addition, there are special rules for the use of free time in Beijing and in some parts of the People's Republic of China (including the total number of working hours and the timetable that is not set).

To set an unplanned work day:

First, obtain the consent of an employee or a trade union organization to establish a non-permanent working day;

Second, to prepare all the necessary documentation;

Thirdly, obtaining the consent of the district labor and social security department.

It is also required that all employees, other than managers, be required to establish permanent non-working hours from the District Department of Labor and Social Welfare [4].

In addition, a number of European laws have been passed in the Federal Republic of Germany to regulate labor relations. In particular, the Law on Working Hours is the basis for the regulation of working hours. This law regulates working hours, breaks, night shifts and working hours in certain areas [5].

In Germany, full-time work can be up to 40 hours per week, up to a maximum of 48 hours. Payment of compensation is also allowed up to 60 hours.

The working week is set for Monday-Saturday, with most employees working Monday through Friday. The law also allows for overtime and shift work. According to the Law on Working Hours [6], many professions provide nighttime hours between 23:00 and 6:00. In the Federal Republic of Germany, employees generally do not work on Sundays a week and on holidays as specified by the law.

In addition, according to this law, the normal working time is 8 hours a day, and under certain conditions this time can be extended up to 10 hours. 6 hours of daily working hours.

Up to 9 hours an employee is entitled to a minimum of 30 minutes minimum lunch time. For a long working day, the minimum break is 45 minutes. These breaks are divided into several parts, but each break must be at least 15 minutes.

An employee cannot work more than 6 hours in a row. At the end of working hours, the employee must have at least 11 hours of free time.

In addition, there are other economically developed countries in the United States (hereinafter referred to as the US), which also applies labor law to federal law.

The basic labor law regulation in the United States is the Fair Labor Standards Act (FLSA) of 1938, which regulates normal working hours, overtime, and legal regulation of underage labor. implied [7].

This law primarily covers the work hours of government employees, as well as those working in the private sector (public and municipal employees, employees working in companies with annual turnover of more than \$ 500,000, interstate commerce workers).

There is no legal definition of working hours in the United States, but the Code of Federal Regulations envisages a working week that may mislead some researchers. According to the law, a working week is defined as working hours with a duration of 168 hours. This means that this definition is a logical fallacy, as the employee does not have time to sleep and rest during the week and is unable to work 168 hours per week.

We can conclude that American law, when describing the work week concept, refers to employee time (daytime, nighttime and overtime). In the US, work week is not always on the calendar. The work week can start from any day of the week and at any time of the day. Typically in all businesses and organizations,

the work week is defined by the employer, as well as the right of the employer to change the workweek if the overtime pay is permanent [8].

“The analysis of the Law on Fair Labor Conditions” provides the following legal norms for working hours:

- normal working hours (40 hours work week);
- reduced working time (for minors);
- part-time (as a rule, in collective agreements. Additional work time is paid in proportion to the time worked) [9].

This law does not limit the employer's right to hire outside workers for 40 hours. It is also envisaged that the employer should pay at least one and a half times the remaining overtime if the employer has more than 40 hours per week [10].

The peculiarities of legal regulation of working hours in the United States are that each state has several powers to regulate labor relations and the right to adopt its own laws. This often worsens the legal status of employees as compared to applicable federal laws.

In some states, over 40 hours work hours are not considered overtime. Additional work is recognized in Minnesota, USA, over 48 hours per week. Kansas law only handles overtime work, which is done beyond 46 hours per week [11].

In fact, these state laws increased their normal working hours by 46 and 48 hours, respectively.

The Fair Labor Conditions Act does not include provisions for the need to obtain written approval from an employee for overtime work, which allows an American employer to hire workers outside of normal working hours without written consent.

In the US, the maximum limits for these cases are not set at the legislative level. Additional work includes any work done outside of a certain hour during the day or week.

If it is not clear who should take the initiative, it can be concluded that overtime work in the United States can be initiated by both an employee and an employer. Based on the foregoing, I would suggest that you make some suggestions for our national legislation.

In addition, it is now the most important legal instrument not only in Uzbekistan, but also in the Commonwealth of Independent States, that the proper scheduling of working hours is appropriate. The regulation of working hours allows the organization of the labor process and the provision of free time

to employees, as well as the effective use of flexible approaches to legal regulation of labor relations both for the employer and the employee.

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